

A Brief Survey of the Synthesis and Bioactivity of Pyrrolocarbazoles, an Emerging Class of Condensed Heterocycles

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Pyrrolocarbazoles arising out of the condensation of the a, b and c bonds of carbazoles and 2,3 and 3,4 bonds of pyrroles have been recently synthesized by different routes, the Diels-Alder cyclization being the prime avenue. One pyrrolocarbazole has also been isolated from a marine sponge. Many of these compounds display a variety of bioactivities including anticancer, antidiabetic, neurotrophic and protein kinase inhibitory properties. The reported syntheses of the various members of this important class of heterocycles have been briefly reviewed.

The last century witnessed the discovery of carbazole from coal tar¹. With the passage of time, carbazole and its derivatives have rapidly developed into a very interesting and useful class of heterocycles. Since 1964, when the first pyranocarbazole derivative, girinimbine, was isolated from a terrestrial plant, *Murraya koenigii*², carbazole, alkaloids, both monocyclic and polycyclic, as well as bis-carbazoles have been reported in ever-increasing numbers, and they constitute an important class of bioactive natural products. In 1977, staurosporine, the first indolo[2,3-*a*]carbazole, was isolated from a *Streptomyces* sp., a microbe cultured from Japanese soil³. By now, more than sixty indolocarbazoles have been isolated from soil microbes, blue-green algae and a slime mould, and they display a wide range of extraordinary and, in some cases, unique biological activities. This has triggered a plethora of multipronged syntheses of indolocarbazoles of mainly [2,3-*a*]-type. We also developed a new synthesis of 5,11-dimethylindolo[3,2-*b*]carbazole, a potential ligand for the receptor of the ubiquitous carcinogen, TCDD⁴.

Our continued interest in the synthesis of condensed carbazoles helped us note that yet another class of annulated carbazoles, viz. pyrrolocarbazoles have, since late eighties, began to emerge as a new class of promising condensed heterocycles. All but one of these are of synthetic origin, the sole exception having been isolated from a marine source. These compounds also display a broad spectrum of bioactivities, viz. anticancer, antidiabetic, neurotrophic and inhibitory properties against protein kinase C, which make these compounds even more important. So far, more than two dozens of reports on the synthesis of the pyrrolocarbazoles have been published, a brief survey of which has been presented in this review. The reported bioactivities of some of these members have also been spelt out to underscore their practical utility.

The isomeric pyrrolocarbazole nuclei that have been reportedly synthesized so far, have been depicted in Scheme 1. The principal methodologies that have been adopted for

the synthesis of various pyrrolocarbazole nuclei are : (A) Borsche cyclization of the hydrazone derived from cyclohexanone and 5-indolyldiazine, (B) photocyclization of 2'-(2-pyrrolyl)-3-vinylindoles in presence of air; (C) condensation of diazotised 2- and 4-aminocarbazoles with ethyl pyruvate; (D) Diels-Alder cyclization of 3- and 2-vinylindoles with carbodienophiles, particularly *N*-phenylmaleimide (NPMI); (E) intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction of a pyrano[4,3-*b*]indol-3-one; (F) dehydrogenative photocyclization of 3-[(2'-aryl)vinyl]indoles; (G) montmorillonite K10 clay-catalyzed condensation of 4-acetyl derivatives of 5-acetoxymethyl or 5-halomethylpyrroles with indoles, (H) Diels-Alder cyclization of C-dienophiles, mainly NPMI, with indole-2,3-quinodimethanes, prepared *in situ* by the thermal cleavage of 1,4-dihydropyrano[3,4-*b*]indol-3-ones, (I) intramolecular Diels-Alder reactions of appropriately substituted indoles.

Although it is desirable to discuss the synthetic approaches to the different isomeric pyrrolocarbazoles classwise, the difficulty of such an approach is that in many cases a single route has led to the formation of more than one kind of pyrrolocarbazoles. For convenience, therefore, the approaches have been discussed in the order stated above, viz. A to I, taking care to restrict the presentations, as far as practicable, to chronological order.

Method A :

In this route⁵, which is incidentally the first report of the synthesis of a pyrrolocarbazole, 1-acetyl-5- and -6-indolyldiazines were condensed with cyclohexanone. The resulting hydrazones were cyclized by heating with ethyl polyphosphate to furnish, after deacetylation and dehydrogenation, pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]- and -[2,3-*b*]carbazoles respectively (Scheme 2).

Method B :

In continuation of their earlier work⁶ on the synthesis of the potent antitumoral agent, CC-1065 by the photocyclization of pyrrole-containing stilbenes in presence of air,

Pyrolocarbazoles abbreviated as PC

Scheme 1

Cava *et al.* synthesized dimethylpyrrolo[3,2-*b*]carbazole (10) by the photocyclodehydrogenation of 2'-(1-methyl-2-pyrrolyl)-1-methyl-3-vinylindole (9)⁷ (Scheme 3). The light-sensitive stilbenoids were purified by flash chromatography, just before use, in a dimly lit room, which renders this method unsuitable for a large-scale synthesis.

• **Method C :**

In this attempt⁸, the Russian workers condensed diazotized 2- and 4-aminocarbazoles with ethyl pyruvate. Subsequent saponification and decarboxylation furnished [2, 3-*b*]-, [3,2-*a*]- and [3,2-*c*]-type pyrolocarbazoles (Scheme 4).

i) Δ ; N_2 ; 30 min
ii) hv (450 W), Quartz filter, Pyrex vessel, 16 hr

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

D.-A. cycloaddition with NPMI, and the reaction stopped at the Michael adduct stage (20), steric factor appearing to prevent cyclization (Scheme 8).

2'-Methoxy-3-vinylindoles, both (*E*)- and (*Z*)-isomers, reacted with NPMI with AlCl_3 as catalyst in a very interesting manner¹¹. The (*E*)-isomer (21) furnished the *endo*-cycloadduct 22, while the (*Z*)-isomer (23) resulted in the

Scheme 9

formation of 26, obviously a double D.-A. adduct. Conceivably, the initially formed D.-A. adduct 24 suffered loss of a molecule of methanol, and the resulting product 25 underwent a second D.-A. cyclization with another molecule of NPMI to form 26 (Scheme 9). In principle, four isomers could arise by the reaction of 25 with NPMI—two with C_3 -symmetry and an enantiomeric pair with C_1 -symmetry. The depicted C_3 -symmetrical configuration of 26 was established by its ^1H -NOESY spectra.

The Diels-Alder reactions of the (1*H*-indol-3-yl)-enacetamides and -endiacetamides (27a-c) at room temperature furnished exclusively the *endo*-cycloadducts, the pyrrolo[3,4-*a*]carbazoles (28a or 28b) with concomitant hydrolysis of the endiacetamide moiety to an enacetamide taking place for 27a and 27c. The thermally more stable triacetyl derivative (27c) reacted with NPMI in toluene under reflux to furnish exclusively the *exo*-adduct (28c), also a pyrrolo[3,4-*a*]carbazole¹² (Scheme 10). An energetically favourable secondary HOMO (diene)-LUMO (dienophile) orbital in-

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Scheme 10

teraction in the D.-A. transition state accounts for the formation of the *endo*-adducts. Special reaction conditions were necessary to prevent solvolysis of the enamides 27 to the more stable 3-acetyl-1*H*-indoles. Successful D.-A. reactions occurred only after using inert gas atmosphere, activated molecular sieves (4 Å) as non-acidic catalysts, very pure anhydrous solvents, and in the strict absence of any acidic component.

Noland *et al.* developed a new synthesis of pyrrolo[3,4-*a*]carbazoles by the D.-A. trapping of 3-vinylindoles (formed

i: M^1 's, EtOH/HCl ; Δ ii DDQ, Dioxan, Δ

Scheme 11

in situ by the condensation of indoles with aldehydes or ketones), followed by dehydrogenation by DDQ of the resulting all *cis*-tetrahydropyrrolo[3,4-*a*]carbazoles¹³ (Scheme 11).

2-Vinylindole itself underwent D.-A. cyclization with NPMI, leading expectedly to the formation of the pyrrolo[3,4-*c*]carbazole (29) after a formal [1,3-*H*]-shift of the initially formed cycloadduct^{14,15} (Scheme 12).

i : NPMI; PhCH₃, Δ

Scheme 12

Selectively functionalized 2-vinylindoles (30a-i) reacted with NPMI to yield Diels-Alder adducts (31), D.-A. ene-products (32), and Michael adducts (33) with high regio- and/or stereoselectivities (Scheme 13). All the cycloaddi-

32 (D.-A. ene product)

i : NPMI

R¹ = H, Me, Ac; R² = H, Me, Ph, OMe, CO₂Me; R³ = H, Me

Scheme 13

tion products were expectedly pyrrolo[3,4-*c*]carbazoles^{15,16}. These workers also studied the synthetic and mechanistic aspects of the reactions of 2-vinylindoles with carbodienophiles, using 1'-methyl-2-vinylindole and 2'-acetyl-2-vinylindole and NPMI¹⁷. MNDO calculations performed on 2-vinylindole disclosed that the aforesaid D.-A. reactions are HOMO (diene)-LUMO (dienophile)-controlled processes.

During the study of the synthesis of fused pyrrolocarbazoles useful for enhancing the function/survival of neuronal cells and inhibition of protein kinase, inflammation

response and hyperproliferative cell growth, an American group of workers prepared an indeno[2,3-*a*]pyrrolo[3,4-*c*]carbazole, depicted below, by the D.-A. cyclization of 2-(2-indenyl)indole with maleimide (MI), followed by

6*H*, 12*H*, 13*H*-Indeno[2,3-*a*]pyrrolo[3,4-*c*]carbazole-5,7(5*H*, 7*H*)-dione

Scheme 14

didehydrogenation of the initially formed tetrahydro derivative¹⁸ (Scheme 14). This condensed PC exhibited a high degree of spinal cord choline acetyl transferase (ChaT) activity as well as inhibition of protein kinase C (IC₅₀ : 0.07 μM).

In a useful application of the D.-A. cycloaddition of selectively functionalized 2-vinylindoles, 1-aminoalkyl-2-[2'(3-thienyl)viny]indole was cyclized with maleimide to

i : [4+2] ii. -H₂ iii : Deprotection

Scheme 15

furnish, after dehydrogenation and deprotection, P[3,4-*c*]C's which were inhibitors of pkC (*in vitro*) at nanomolar levels¹⁹ (Scheme 15).

Method E :

In their effort to develop a new synthesis of the staurosporine aglycone (36a) without the use of protecting groups on the indole and lactam nitrogens, Moody *et al.* synthesized the pyrrolo[3,4-*c*] carbazole (35a) by the intramolecular D.-A. reaction of the pyranoidolone (34a),

followed by dehydrogenation of the resulting dihydrocarbazole²⁰. The model pyrrolocarbazoles **35b** and **35c** were also prepared analogously (Scheme 16). As designed, nitrene-mediated ring closure of **35a** furnished the targeted aglycone **36a**. The crucial starting materials **34** were prepared from ethyl indole-2-acetate in a few steps.

Method F :

Italian workers developed an easy entry to a 3-[(2'-aryl)vinyl]indole which was then photocyclized to produce, after *in situ* dehydrogenation of the resulting dihydro[*a*]-annulated carbazole, the pyrrolo[3,2-*a*]carbazole (**37**)²¹ (Scheme 17).

Method G :

A convergent and general synthesis of pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]carbazoles (**40**) was developed by Shannon *et al.*²² by the condensation of indoles with 5-acetoxymethyl or alkoxy-methyl-4-acetylpyrroles (**38**) using Montmorillonite K10 clay as catalyst (Scheme 18). NOE difference spectra proved that the products were of [3,2-*b*]-type and not the [2,3-*b*]-isomer.

Heating the reactants for a shorter period furnished the corresponding 3-[2-pyrrolyl]methyl]indoles (**39**) which go via spirocyclic intermediates to the pyrrolocarbazoles (Scheme 19). Many of the prepared pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]carbazoles possessed antitumour activity.

Scheme 17

R¹ = H, Me, F; R² = H, Me, R³ = Et, CH₂Ph; X = OAc, OR
 i. M. K10 clay (excess); ClCH₂CH₂Cl, Δ

Scheme 18

A subsequent reinvestigation of these reactions additionally culminated in the isolation of a pyrrolo[2,3-*b*]carbazole in minor amount²³ (Scheme 20). A study of the chemical shifts of C(3)- and C(4)-methyls revealed that in the [3,2-*b*]-isomer, the difference between the chemical shifts of the two methyls is 0.01 ppm, whereas the same in the case of the [2,3-*b*]-isomer is 0.22 ppm. This criterion was found to be diagnostic for differentiating the two isomeric PC's.

These workers further established some other aspects of such clay-catalyzed conditions. Firstly, the presence of elec-

tron-donating groups in indole led to the formation of increasing proportions of the [2,3-*b*]-type pyrrolocarbazoles. Secondly, a 4- or 6-methyl or methoxy group in the indole ring enhances electrophilic substitution at C-2, thereby increasing the relative proportion of the [2,3-*b*]-isomer. But, an *N*-methyl group in indole restores C-3 as the site of electrophilic substitution (Scheme 21). Also, with 5- or 6-haloindoles, the products were the [3,2-*b*]-PC's with little or none of the [2,3-*b*]-isomers. Thirdly, M. K10 clay is not essential for the said condensations. *p*-TsOH, for example, led to the condensation of indole and 38 to furnish the corresponding [3,2-*b*]-type PC as the only isomer formed in 14% yield.

Many pyrrolocarbazoles of both [3,2-*b*]- and [2,3-*b*]-type, prepared in this fashion, were later found to be promising antitumor compounds and have since been patented²⁴.

These PC's were effective against human breast cancer cells, epidermal carcinoma cells and melanoma cells, but with low toxicity against normal cells.

Following this route, the same authors have very recently synthesized the [3,2-*b*]- and [2,3-*b*]pyrrolocarbazoles (41 and 42), the analogs of 8,10-dimethoxyellipticine, albeit in very poor yields, viz. 5 and 4% respectively²⁵ (Scheme 22).

Method H :

This route involving D.-A. cyclization of indole-2,3-quinodimethanes with NPMI, leading to pyrrolo[3,4-*b*]carbazoles (44 and 45), was developed in successive years first by Pindur²⁶ and then by Moody²⁷. The quinodimethanes were prepared *in situ* by the thermal cleavage of 1,4-dihydropyrano[3,4-*b*]indol-3-ones (43) (Scheme 23). The fully aromatic carbazoles, 44 have co-planar frame-

works and are potential DNA-intercalators²⁶.

Method I :

An elegant synthesis of the pyrrolo[3,4-*c*]carbazoles, 46 and 47, by the intramolecular Diels-Alder reactions of appropriately substituted indole derivatives has recently been reported from the DuPont Merck Pharmaceutical Co. re-

Scheme 24

search laboratories²⁸ (Scheme 24).

This completes the description of the fundamental methodologies that have been reported till mid-'96 for the synthesis of various pyrrolocarbazoles. Very recently, the pyrrolocarbazole 35b²⁰, described in method-E, was converted to a number of its derivatives (Scheme 25), and these were tested for neurotropic activities by measuring the enhancement of ChaT activity in spinal cord cultures²⁹. It was observed that 35b, its indole *N*-methyl derivative, the

Scheme 25

related 7-oxolactam, and the 3-bromo derivative possess neurotropic activity, the bromo derivative displaying highest activity even at low concentrations (146% of control at 1 μM).

A number of 1,2,3,5-tetrahydro-1-oxopyrrolo[3,4-*b*] and [3,4-*c*]carbazoles⁴ were prepared from the pyrrolocar-

Scheme 26

bazolediones (Scheme 26). Many of these PC's displayed potent anticancer activity against solid tumors but having low toxicity. Thus, 48 and 49 inhibited the growth of solid tumors at MIC of 1.56 and 0.08 μg ml⁻¹, respectively³⁰.

Recently, pyrrolo[3,4-*c*]carbazoles were reportedly prepared by the intramolecular Michael reaction of appropriately functionalized indoles³¹.

Japanese workers have reported in 1993 the first natural occurrence of a few functionalized pyrrolo[2,3-*c*]carbazoles from a marine sponge, a *Dictyodentrella* sp.³². These PC's have been proven to be inhibitors of aldose reductase which catalyzes the reduction of aldoses to polyols, the intracellular accumulation of which may result in diabetes. Aldose reductase inhibitors thus provide both prevention and cure of such ailments. Indeed, some of the isolated PC's are in clinical trials as antidiabetic agents (Scheme 27).

IC₅₀ (against bovine lens a. r.) : 1.12 × 10⁻⁷ M

Scheme 27

A passage through this overview should clearly reflect that pyrrolocarbazoles are full of promise from the points of view of both synthesis and bioactivity. The overview, the first of its kind on PC's and as presented herein, is by no means exclusive. The very important group of *Aspidosperma* alkaloids which contain fused pyrrolocarbazole nucleus have not been included. It would perhaps be pertinent to mention that the authors of this review are currently engaged in the development of newer synthetic routes to pyrrolocarbazoles.

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